

THE INFLUENCE OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH CULTURE ON THE RESEARCH COMPETENCE OF LECTURERS OF KYAMBOGO UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of institutional research culture on research competence of lecturers of Kyambogo University. Using a correlational research design to collect data and analyse data from a sample of 192 teaching staff. The data were analysed using SPSS for descriptive statistics and SmartPLS was used to test the hypotheses and structural equation modelling. Descriptive results indicated that the majority of the respondents were males (54.7%). Concerning age range, the majority 66.7% were aged 40 years and above while the rest (33.3%) were below 40 years and the majority (60.9%) were PhD holders. Inferential results revealed that institutional research culture had a positive and significant influence on lecturers' research competences. It explained 33.6% of the variation in research competence of lecturers. Therefore, institutional research culture is very central in fostering the research competences of lecturers. Institutional managers should nurture a culture that enhances the research competence of lecturers.

KEYWORDS

Institutional Research Culture, Research, Research Competence

1. INTRODUCTION

Research competence of lecturers is a challenge globally with a significant number of them facing a challenge of originality, innovation, skills and scientific expertise for 21st century researchers [1]. Many lecturers exhibit an inability to communicate, let alone publish in reputable peer-reviewed international journals [2]. Consequently, they are unable to meet the expanding research need, expectations of research at a global scale and their key performance indicators in regards to research at the institutional level remain wanting. For example, only 10 countries globally that is China, Germany, Italy, United Kingdom (UK), and United States of America (USA) among others, contribute to 87 per cent of the academic papers published globally and over 36 per cent of these are attributed to only the USA and China [3]. In Africa, the pace at which quality research output is generated is still low. For example, the continent has for decades stagnated at 1 per cent of research output which is much less compared to the world's research output [4]. Researchers attribute the limited research output to several factors including inadequate research competence of the researchers and institutional research culture. Research competence refers to a set of proficiencies to undertake high-quality studies or the ability to identify a problem, collect data using selected and appropriate instruments, identifying an appropriate method of manipulating data, testing of significance, and interpreting the findings [5; 6]. Institutional research culture refers to both the tangible and non-tangible components of the institution that aid productivity [7]. In this study, drawing from the theory of organisational

culture, institutional research culture was denoted as research artefact, the research espoused beliefs and the research basic underlying assumptions.

Research competence is fundamental in the development of intellectual, communicative, creative abilities and design skills of faculties, institutions and students. Individuals who attain research competence have an intensified cognitive activity and they develop the desire to learn more in order to transform the surrounding reality [6]. In recognition of the importance of research competence, universities in Uganda have put mechanisms to promote research competence of academic staff. For instance, in partnership with stakeholders, universities have been allocating funds to support multidisciplinary research and innovations [8]. In particular, Kyambogo University has an innovation and research policy of 2014 [9], and Directorate of Research and Grants, and infrastructure to support research. In spite of the above effort, research competence of lecturers remained low as indicated by their low publication capabilities, inability to win research project funds, limited internal collaborations and low ability to link research to industry [10,11,12,13]. It was reported that 81 per cent and 79 per cent of the lecturers at Kyambogo University hardly authored a book or a book chapter respectively [12]. Furthermore, the Sectoral Committee of Education and Sports in Uganda in their report of 2023/2024 indicated limited evidence on key results of the research activities yet research was highlighted among other areas of focus [14]. These attracted the need for this study to examine the factors relating to it, specifically looking at the influence of institutional research culture on research competence of lecturers. If the study was not conducted, the managers of educational institutions and the lecturers who are the target group for this study would miss a reference point for advocating for desired institutional research culture and the new insights that this study highlights would not be realised and so would be the National Development Plan three, Uganda's vision 2040 that clearly point out the need for quality research and innovations for socio-economic development.

2. METHODS

2.1. Study Design and Sample Size

The study used a correlational research design to provide a correlation coefficient between variables. It used a self-administered questionnaire to collect data among 200 teaching staff of Kyambogo University who were sampled using Krejcie and Morgan table for a known population [15] from study population of 405 teaching staff of Kyambogo University [16]. The lecturers included the professors, associate professors, senior lecturers, lecturers, assistant lecturers and teaching assistants were best suited for this study because one of their cardinal roles is to conduct research. These were selected from their various schools and faculties using simple random sampling technique by assigning random numbers in excel and taking the desired sample. This permitted every member of the faculty to have an equal chance of being selected for the study.

2.2. Validity and Reliability of Data

A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) for both convergent validity and discriminant validity were determined. Convergent validity was determined using average variance extracted (AVE) at > 0.5 while discriminant validity was determined using Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) below 0.90 [17]. Reliability was determined using Cronbach's alpha (α) and composite reliability (CR). The values ranging from 0.7 to 0.9 were considered satisfactory.

2.3. Data Management and Ethical Considerations

The data collected was coded, entered in the computer using SPSS Version 30.0. It was screened and missing data together with outliers were deleted. Descriptive statistics were analyzed by the use of SPSS. However, hypothesis (Institutional research culture has a significant positive influence on the research competence of lecturers) was analyzed using SmartPLS 4.1 and both the path and structural equation models were presented. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Directorate of Research and Graduate Training of Kyambogo University. The researcher ensured ethical standards during data collection. In terms of privacy, the lecturers were asked not to disclose their identity anywhere on the research tool. Concerning anonymity, the research tools were given anonymous numbers so no one could ever associate the tool with the respondent. As far as confidentiality was concerned, the lecturers were informed that the shared information would be strictly used for academic purpose and no one else would ever get to know who responded to which tool. The tools would be stored in a very secure place and destroyed after the work the candidate has graduated and disseminated findings. In reference to honesty, this article presents the data collected as was collected.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Background Characteristics

The background information of the respondents including their age range, gender, highest level of education, designation at Kyambogo university.

Table 1. Background Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	105	54.7
	Female	87	45.3
	Total	192	100
Age range	29 and below	14	7.3
	30 to 39	50	26.0
	40 to 49	81	42.2
	50 and above	47	24.5
	Total	192	100
Education level	Bachelor	10	5.2
	Masters	65	33.9
	PhD	117	60.9
	Total	192	100
Designation	Professor	1	0.5
	Associate Professor	7	3.6
	Senior Lecturer	4	2.1
	Lecturer	105	54.7
	Assistant Lecturer	65	33.9
	Teaching Assistant	10	5.2
	Total	192	100
	Experience	Less than 3 years	15
3 to five years		53	27.6
6 to 10 years		75	39.1
More than 10 years		49	25.5
Total		192	100

The results in Table1 indicate that the majority of lecturers who participated in the study were male (54.7%), while the females were 45.3%. despite the males being more represented, the percentage of females was considerable, an indication that the results are representative of both gender groups. The results on age range of lecturers indicated that the greater proportion were 40 to 49 years of age (42.2%) followed by those age 30 to 39 (26.0%), then 50 years and above (24.5%), and those aged 29 and below (7.3%). These results indicated that lecturers below 29 years are generally few compared to those above 30 years. They also revealed that the larger majority of lecturers above 30 years of age are generally less divergent in their various age groups an indication that the results were representative of the lecturers' age groups. The results on the lecturers' highest level of education indicated that the majority percentage (60.9%) were PhD holders while 33.9% were masters' degree holders and 5.2% had bachelor's degree. The fact that the majority percentage of lecturers were PhD holders gives a clear indication of representativeness of data.

3.2. Institutional Research Culture and Research Competence

The first objective of the study sought to examine the influence of institutional research culture on the research competence of lecturers of Kyambogo University. Institutional research culture was studied in terms of research artefacts, research espoused beliefs and values, and research basic underlying assumptions. The descriptive results of the three constructs follow as well as the average index and inferential analysis examining the influence of institutional research culture on the research competence of lecturers.

3.2.1. Research Artefacts

Research artefacts was conceived as the first element of institutional research culture and was studied using 5 indicators. The results follow in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for Research Artefacts

Research artefacts		SD	D	MA	A	SA	Mean
The university has adequate research infrastructure	F	26	47	39	42	38	3.10
	%	13.5	24.5	20.3	21.9	19.8	
There is a well-furnished lab/research room with research equipment necessary for research in my discipline at my university	F	28	63	71	16	14	2.61
	%	14.6	32.8	37.0	8.3	7.3	
The management of the university highly values staff research creativeness and innovation	F	1	40	59	66	26	3.40
	%	0.5	20.8	30.7	34.4	13.5	
In this university there are clear structures for managing research	F	34	25	73	45	15	2.91
	%	17.7	13.0	38.0	23.4	7.8	
It is a constant concern to keep the research technology up to date in this university	F	20	33	71	52	16	3.06
	%	10.4	17.2	37.0	27.1	8.3	

The results in Table 2 on whether the university had adequate research infrastructure cumulatively showed that the larger percentage (41.7%) agreed while 20.3% moderately agreed and 63.8% disagreed. The moderate mean of 3.10 which is close to 3 on the five-point Likert scale used in the study corresponded to moderately agree. Therefore, lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed to whether the university had adequate research infrastructure. As to whether there was a well-furnished lab/research room with research equipment necessary for, the majority (47.4%) disagreed while 37.0% moderately agreed and 15.6% agreed. The low mean of 2.61 suggested that lecturers almost disagreed to the statement that there was a well-furnished

lab/research room with research equipment necessary for research in the various academic disciplines of lecturers.

With regards to whether the management of the university highly valued staff research creativeness and innovation, the larger percentage (47.9%) agreed, 30.7% moderately agreed and 21.3% disagreed. The moderate mean of 3.40 suggested that lecturers were neither agreed nor disagreed to the statement that the management of the university highly valued staff research creativeness and innovation. As to whether the university had clear structures for managing research, relatively equal percentage were observed. Results indicated that 38.0% moderately agreed, 31.2% agreed and 30.0% disagreed. The moderate mean 2.91 implied that lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed to the statement that the university had clear structures for managing research. Regarding whether the university was concerned about keeping the research technology up to date, there were relatively equal percentages whereby 37.0% moderately agreed, 35.4% agreed while 27.6 disagreed. The moderate mean of 3.06 suggested that the lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed to the statement that the university was concerned about keeping the research technology up to date.

3.2.2. Espoused beliefs and values

Espoused beliefs and values were conceived as the second element of institutional research culture and was studied using nine indicators. The results follow in Table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics for Research Espoused Beliefs and Values

Espoused beliefs and values		SD	D	MA	A	SA	Mean
I am familiar with the research policy of my university	F	22	39	54	41	36	3.16
	%	11.5	20.3	28.1	21.4	18.8	
The research agenda of the university has influenced my research activities and skills	F	26	40	66	45	15	2.91
	%	13.5	20.8	34.4	23.4	7.8	
The research seminars at my department have given me an opportunity to share my research findings	F	9	52	89	20	22	2.97
	%	4.7	27.1	46.4	10.4	11.5	
The university exchange programmes have improved my research competence	F	45	45	63	27	12	2.56
	%	23.4	23.4	32.8	14.1	6.3	
My research activities are regularly monitored by my university	F	39	47	63	18	25	2.70
	%	20.3	24.5	32.8	9.4	13.0	
I have been supported by my university to access external funding for my research	F	22	97	55	21	15	2.63
	%	11.5	41.1	28.6	10.9	7.8	
I have been supported by the university to access university research funds internally	F	12	60	73	35	12	2.87
	%	6.3	31.3	38.0	18.2	6.3	
I have a research mentor at my university	F	21	26	57	54	34	3.28
	%	10.9	13.5	29.7	28.1	17.7	
I have a core research team at my university	F	13	32	55	77	15	3.26
	%	6.8	16.7	28.6	40.1	7.8	

The results in Table 3 on whether the lecturers were familiar with the research policy of the university cumulatively showed that the larger percentage (40.2%) agreed while 28.1% moderately agreed and 31.8% disagreed. The moderate mean of 3.16 which is close to 3 on the five-point Likert scale used in the study corresponded to moderately agree. Therefore, lecturers were averagely familiar with the research policy of the university. As to whether the research agenda of the university had influenced their research activities and skills, relatively similar percentages were observed where 34.4% of the participants moderately agreed, 34.3% disagreed and 31.20% agreed. The moderate mean of 2.91 suggested that lecturers moderately agreed that

the research agenda of the university had influenced their research activities and skills. With regards to whether the research seminars at the department had given lecturers an opportunity to share research findings, the larger percentage (46.4%) moderately agreed, 31.8% disagreed and 21.9% agreed. The moderate mean of 2.97 suggested that lecturers were neither agreed nor disagreed to the research seminars at the department had given them an opportunity to share their research findings.

As to whether the university exchange programmes had improved research competence of lecturers, the cumulative majority percentage (46.8%) disagreed. These were followed by 32.8% who moderately agreed, 20.4% who agreed. The moderate mean 2.56 implied that lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed to the statement that the university exchange programmes had improved their research competences. Regarding whether research activities were regularly monitored by the university, a cumulative majority percentage (44.8%) disagreed, 32.8% moderately agreed while 22.4% agreed. The moderate mean of 2.70 suggested that the lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed that their research activities were regularly monitored by the university. With respect to whether lecturers had been supported by the university to access external funding to enable them conduct research, a cumulative majority percentage (52.6%) disagreed, 28.6% moderately agreed and 18.7% agreed. The moderate mean of 2.63 suggested that the lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed that they had been supported by the university to access external research funding.

With regards to whether lecturers had been supported by the university to access university research funds internally, relatively similar percentages 38.0% and 37.6% moderately agreed and disagreed respectively while 24.5% agreed. The moderate mean of 2.87 suggested that the lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed that they had been supported by the university to access internal research funding. Concerning whether lecturers had a research mentor at the university, a cumulative majority percentage (45.8%) agreed, while 29.7% moderately agreed and 24.4% disagreed. The moderate mean of 3.28 suggested that lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed that they had research mentors at the university. As to whether lecturers had a core research team at the university, a cumulative majority percentage (47.9%) agreed, while 29.7% moderately agreed while 23.5% disagreed. The moderate mean of 3.26 suggested that lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed that they had a core research team at the university.

3.2.3. Research Basic Underlying Assumptions

Research basic underlying assumptions was conceived as the third element of institutional research culture and was studied using seven indicators. The results follow in Table 4.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics for Research Basic Underlying Assumptions

Research Basic Underlying Assumptions		SD	D	MA	A	SA	Mean
The university has established support systems for the staff to conduct research	F	27	32	65	32	36	3.09
	%	14.1	16.7	33.9	16.7	18.8	
In this university mutual research responsibility and shared objectives are emphasized	F	3	48	83	39	19	3.12
	%	1.6	25.0	43.2	20.3	9.9	
The university research objectives have been communicated to all staff	F	1	31	58	80	22	3.47
	%	0.5	16.1	30.2	41.7	11.5	
In this university staff members are involved in research decision making processes	F	4	56	57	56	19	3.16
	%	2.1	29.2	29.7	29.2	9.9	
The university encourages staff to share ideas and suggestions on research	F	14	42	52	62	22	3.19
	%	7.3	21.9	27.1	32.3	11.5	
In this university, a mutual and trusting relationship between management and subordinates was established on research issues	F	8	52	51	62	19	3.17
	%	4.2	27.1	26.6	32.3	9.9	
The university has put support mechanism for staff to get highly involved in research	F	5	38	34	43	72	3.72
	%	2.6	19.8	17.7	22.4	37.5	

The results in Table 4 on whether the university had well established support systems for the staff to conduct research lecturers, showed that the relatively similar percentages were obtained whereby 35.5% agreed, 33.9% moderately agreed and 30.8% disagreed respectively. The moderate mean of 3.09 was close to 3 which on the five-point Likert scale used in the study corresponded to moderately agreed. Therefore, were not sure whether or not the university had well established support systems for the staff to conduct research. As to whether there was mutual research responsibility and shared objectives were emphasized, lecturers involve students in discussions about academic documents, the majority of the respondents (43.2%) moderately agreed while 30.2% agreed and 26.6% disagreed. The moderate mean of 3.12 suggested lecturers were not sure whether the university had a mutual research responsibility and emphasized such objectives with lecturers.

Concerning whether university had communicated research objectives to all staff members. the larger percentage (53.2%) agreed, 30.2% moderately agreed and 16.6% disagreed respectively. The moderate mean of 3.47 suggested that lecturers were not sure of whether the university had communicated its research objectives to all staff members. With respect to whether the staff members were involved in research decision making processes, the larger percentage (39.1%) agreed while 31.3% disagreed and 29.7% moderately agreed. The moderate mean of 3.16 implied that lectures neither agreed nor disagreed to being involved in research decision making processes.

Regarding whether the university encouraged staff to share ideas and suggestions on research, the larger percentage (43.8%) agreed while 29.2% disagreed and 27.1% moderately agreed. The moderate mean 3.19 suggested that the lecturers neither agreed nor disagreed that the university encouraged staff to share ideas and suggestions on research. With regard to whether there was a mutual and trusting relationship between management and subordinates on research, the majority percentage (42.2%) agreed while 31.3 disagreed and 26.6% moderately agreed. The average mean of 3.17 meant that there was a fairly mutual and trusting relationship between management subordinates on research. As to whether the university had put support mechanism in place for staff to get highly involved in research, the larger percentage (59.9%) agreed while 22.4% disagreed and 17.7% moderately agreed. The high mean of 3.72 suggested that lecturers appreciated that the university had provided support mechanisms for them to engage in research activities.

3.2.4. Institutional Research Culture

To find out how overall the lecturers rated institutional research culture at Kyambogo University, an average index was calculated for the indicators of three constructs measuring the variable. The histogram (Figure 1) presents the overall mean and shows the normality of the results.

Figure 1. Histogram for Institutional Research Culture

The results in Figure 1 show a mean score of 3.40 and a standard deviation of 0.593. The average mean indicates that the lecturers considered the university’s research culture to be moderate. The low standard deviation suggested that the data were normally distributed, confirming the assumption of normality required for parametric analysis. Therefore, the data was suitable for linear analysis.

3.2.5. Institutional Research Culture Structural Model

To establish the measures of institutional research culture, a structural equation model was developed. Figure 2 shows the appropriate indicators of the constructs measuring the variable.

Figure 2. Institutional Research Culture Structural Equation Model

The results in Figure 2 shows that institutional research culture was considered a tri-dimensional concept covering research artefacts, research espoused beliefs and values and research basic underlying assumptions. Factor loadings show that for research artefacts, 5 indicators of the 6 were retained (ATE1 to ATE5) with one indicator (ATE6) dropped. For research espoused beliefs and values, six (EBV1 to EBV6), out of the nine indicators were retained with 3 indicators (EBV7, EBV8 and EBV9) dropped. For the research basic underlying assumptions, five of the seven indicators that is (BUA, BAU2, BUA4, BUA5, BUA6) were retained whereas BAU3 and BUA7 were dropped. All the indicators that were retained had factor loadings above 0.50 which is the lowest accepted level [18]. Therefore, the retained indicators for the tri-dimensions in the model were portray valid measures.

3.2.6. Structural Equation Model for institutional Research Culture and Research Competence of Lecturers

The structural equation model (Figure 3) displays the influence of institutional research culture on the research competence of lecturers of Kyambogo University.

Figure 3. Structural Equation Model for Institutional Research Culture and Research Competence of Lecturers Structural Equation Model

The structural equation model (Figure 3) for institutional research culture and lecturers' research competence reveals that in the model institutional research culture comprised of three measures that are research artefacts, research espoused beliefs and values as well as research basic underlying assumptions. Research competence comprised of two components, namely reflective abilities and communication skills while the measures of knowledge of research content, and research review skills were dropped. The model results in Table 4.9 include beta coefficients (β s), coefficients of determination (R^2 and adjusted R^2), t statistics and the p-values. The coefficients of determination reveal the predictive power of institutional research culture on lecturers' research competences. The three hypotheses to the effect that research artefacts (H_1), research espoused beliefs and values (H_2) as well as research basic underlying assumptions (H_3) have significant influence on research competence were tested. The structural equation model path estimates are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Institutional Research Culture and Research Competence Path Estimates

	β	T	P values
ATE \rightarrow RC	0.254	2.128	0.033
BUA \rightarrow RC	0.231	2.748	0.006
EBV \rightarrow RC	0.212	2.037	0.042
R2 = 0.347			
R2 Adjusted =0.336			

The structural equation model estimates (Table 5) indicate that research artefacts ($\beta = 0.254$, $t = 2.128$, $p = 0.033 < 0.05$), research basic underlying assumptions ($\beta = 0.231$, $t = 2.748$, $p = 0.006 < 0.05$) and research espoused beliefs and values ($\beta = 0.212$, $t = 2.037$, $p = 0.042 < 0.05$) had a positive and significant influence on lecturers' research competences. The adjusted R^2 showed that the three institutional research culture aspects, explained 33.6% (adjusted $R^2 = 0.336$) of the variation in research competence of lecturers. The magnitude of respective betas showed that research artefacts had a more significant influence on lecturers' research competence than research basic underlying assumptions and research espoused beliefs respectively. However, with all aspects of institutional research culture having a positive and significant influence on research competence, it was suggested that the hypothesis to the effect that institutional research culture has a significant influence on research competence of lecturers of Kyambogo University was accepted.

4. DISCUSSION

The hypothesis test results showed that institutional research culture in terms of research artefacts, research espoused beliefs and values as well basic underlying assumptions had a positive and significant influence on research competence of lecturers. This finding was consistent with the Theory of Organisational Culture (TOC) [19] on which this study was based that an organization with a well-established culture supported by a shared vision and mission, protocols, guidelines, values, infrastructure, and positive working conditions facilitate the achievement of objectives. Similarly, a study by Rahman (2024) among lecturers at the Institute of Teacher Education in Malaysia reported a positive and significant influence of institutional support to the lecturers' motivation and skills to conduct research.

The finding of the study also accords with the findings of [20] who found out that working conditions were positive predictors of research competence among the research teachers and research supervisors in high schools in the Philippines. The positive working conditions were those that are that offered adequate and appropriate research infrastructure and were supportive in terms of research funding, seed money, offering research expert talks, workshops, and seminars. Teachers considered annual recognition of those who had exemplary research skills to be highly influential as far as gaining research competence is concerned. Research collaboration and monitoring also influenced research competence of teachers. In a similar manner, findings of the study by [21] at Vietnam National University reported that provision of resources and university policies are the most influential factors affecting research productivity of lecturers. These findings align with those by [10] who revealed that policy support had a positive and significant relationship with research productivity within which one of the constructs was research skills. In their study, research policy support was reported as moderate with a mean value of 3.07. This implies that institutions have the role to provide, share and enforce clear-cut guidelines, and protocols on research so as to improve research competence and productivity among the faculty.

Consistent with the finding of the study, [22] revealed that institutional research culture significantly influenced scientific publication capacity and performance in terms of both quality and quantity among lecturers of Telkom University in Indonesia. Also, a study that was conducted in five different institutions in the province of Albay in Philippines reported that institutional support, research orientation and leadership practices impacted research productivity and overall research competences of faculty members [23]. Accordingly, offering a clear research agenda, research-related capacity development opportunities, research funding, and faculty research writing aptitude regularly would enhance research competence of lecturers and eventual research productivity. A study by [24] on institutional culture emphasizes that institution's leadership should promote and enforce the mission statement in written and spoken discourse such as letters and speeches from time to time, more so when new members have joined the institution. In view of consistent findings with previous scholars, institutional research culture significantly influences research competence of lecturers.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion Institutional research culture is very central in fostering the research competences of lecturers. This is when institutions provide research artefacts in form of infrastructure, such as well facilitated and up to date libraries, laboratories and supplies; and a conducive work environment that fosters teamwork. It also covers when institutions promote and enforce research policy, ethical standards, research agenda, ensure that the mission statement, goals, objectives and values embrace research. This is also when lecturers' attitude, perceptions and thoughts towards research activities are positive and they prioritize it among other institutional activities. It is recommended that managers in higher institutions of learning should nurture a research culture that enhances the research competence of lecturers. The institutions should provide infrastructure that facilitates research activities for example update libraries, laboratory supplies and equipment as well as ensuring working conditions that are conducive in terms of research such as internal research funding and identifying external funding sources and those that promote research collaborations such as mentorship pairs. Further studies could consider a qualitative approach to investigate the experiences of lecturers in conducting research given the prevalent institutional research culture.

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